

Nolle Prosequi: Comparative Assessment of the power of the Attorney-General in Nigeria and the United Kingdom

Simeon Olaosebikan Oni, Ph.D

Department of Public and International Law, Faculty of Law
Lead City University, Ibadan
simeonolaoni@gmail.com

Oyedokun Godwin Emmanuel, Ph.D

Professor in the Department of Management and Accounting,
Lead City University, Ibadan
godwinoye@yahoo.com

Abstract:

Introduction: *Nolle prosequi* is a Latin word which means “do not wish to proceed.” The court in the case of **Ogbonna v Ogbonna & Anor**¹ defined *Nolle Prosequi* as a formal notice of discontinuance of an action lodge by the prosecution. It is only the Attorney-General that has the constitutional power to discontinue a criminal proceeding.²

The Attorney General enjoys several constitutional and statutory powers amongst which is the power to initiate, take over and terminate legal proceedings in all courts in Nigeria except a court martial. The power to terminate legal proceedings is known as the power of *nolle prosequi*. This has continued to dominate legal and political discourse because of the perceived abuse of the power by unscrupulous Attorney-Generals.

The main reason for this principle of law is the power that initiate a case should also have the power to terminate it. At Common Law the power to prosecute all criminal cases other than Court Martial is vested in the Attorney-General.³ When *nolle prosequi* is entered in a case, it is a legal notice to the court that the Attorney-General has decided to abandon the prosecution or the lawsuit.

Keywords: Nolle Prosequi, Attorney General, Nigeria, United Kingdom,

¹ (2014) LPELR-CA/K/200/2008

² *Akala v FRN* (2014) LPELR-CA/I/154/2013

³ *London County Council v A.G.* 1902 A.C. 165.

Prosecutorial Powers of the Attorney-General in English Law

It was a fundamental doctrine of English constitutional law that “in the exertion ... of those prerogatives, which the law has given him, the King is irresistible and absolute, according to the forms of the Constitution.”⁴ The origin of the office of Attorney-General in England is usually traced to the thirteenth century when, King’s Attorney or King’s Serjeant was responsible for maintaining the interests of the King in the royal courts. The establishment of the office of the Attorney-General predates constitutional development it sprung out from the Common Law in England.

At the earliest time, the king was seen as the fountain of justice as he entertained petitions in his courts in matters affecting the rights of the people. Petitions were becoming too much for the king alone to attend to. The king at the time was the first common law judge and was also looked upon by the people as an institution that can do no wrong and this was expressed in the maxim *rex non potest peccare*.⁵ The maxim later ceased to be a defence for wrongs committed by the king or his servants in the course of effecting the king’s order and it alternatively became “the king must not, was not allowed, was not entitled to do wrong”⁶ With time, the King began to entertain petitions against himself and without bias he would comment *fiat justitia ruat caelum* which means “let justice be done though the heavens fall.” It was impossible for the king to represent himself in the petitions that involved him or his servants. Hence, the need for an attorney for the king became necessary. Consequently, the Attorney-General enjoyed a position of omnipotence in the exercise of the King's prerogative prosecutorial powers.

The expression “Attorney-General” meant no more than a general agent or representative.⁷ He performed not more than the function of representing the king in petitions against the Crown.

⁴ Blackstone, *Commentaries on the Laws of England*, 16th ed. Butterworths, London, vol 1, 250, 1825.

⁵ Dicey A.V, *Introduction to the Study of the Law of the Constitution*, 10th ed, Macmillan, London Pg. 425, 1959.

⁶ Eugene Erlich, *Proceedings against the Crown*, pp.126-137.

⁷ Fitz James Stephen, *History of the Criminal Law of England Vol.1* Pg. 499.

Since it was inconceivable for the king to appear in his suits, he could only sue or be sued by his Attorney who was then addressed as the King's Attorney.⁸ There was a change in the use of the expression "king's attorney" in 1461 when John Herbert was appointed that the term "Attorney-General" was used for the first time in England.

The functions performed by the present day Attorney-General differ substantially from what their functions used to be in the common law period. However, it must be pointed out that the functions performed by the modern day Attorney-General is as a result of constitutional development. In England, at the end of the 19th century, it became clear that the Attorney-General was solely responsible for the commencement of criminal cases and also all civil suits by or against the Crown were (and still are) undertaken by the Attorney-General.

By virtue of his position as a law officer of the crown, the Attorney-General, continues to practice as a barrister with the crown as his only client. He is recognised by the bar as the leader of the legal profession. He has control of the office of public prosecutions, which gives advice on and often conducts criminal prosecutions. Certain offences can be prosecuted only with the approval of the Attorney-General⁹ and he alone has the right to stay criminal proceedings in the superior courts. This power to stay criminal proceedings is known as the exercise of *nolle prosequi*.

In the case of *Gouriet v Union of Post Office Workers*,¹⁰ *per Viscount Dilhorne* restated the principle in this oft-quoted dictum:

The Attorney-General has many powers and duties. He may stop any prosecution on indictment by entering a nolle prosequi. He merely has to sign a piece of paper saying that he does not wish the prosecution to continue. He need not give any reasons. He

⁸ Professor Sayles, *The King's Parliament of England*, 1974.

⁹ Prevention of Crimes Act 1906 & Public Bodies Corrupt Practices Act 1889.

¹⁰ 1978 AC 435 at 487

can direct the institution of a prosecution and direct the Director of Public Prosecutions to take over the conduct of any criminal proceedings and he may tell him to offer no evidence. In the exercise of these powers he is not subject to direction by his ministerial colleagues or to control and supervision by the courts.

However, the judgments in the ***Gouriet's case*** and similar cases are a reflection of past judicial refusal to enquire into the way in which a prerogative power had been exercised in England. All these have changed with the progressive development of judicial review, the English courts have been more willing to review the exercise of discretionary power, whether derived from statute or the prerogative.

This change in judicial attitude reached its climax in ***Council of Civil Service Unions v Minister for the Civil Service***¹¹ where House of Lords laid to rest the view that all prerogative powers are beyond judicial review. **Lord Diplock** stated that:

no reason why simply because a decision-making power is derived from a common law and not a statutory source, it should for that reason only be immune from judicial review.

Rather, according to **Lord Scarman**

*The law relating to judicial review has now reached the stage where it can be said with confidence that, if the subject matter in respect of which prerogative power is exercised is justiciable, that is to say if it is a matter upon which the court can adjudicate, the exercise of the power is subject to review in accordance with the principles developed in respect of the review of the exercise of statutory power. ... Today, therefore, the controlling factor in determining whether the exercise of prerogative power is subject to judicial review is not its source but its subject matter.*¹²

¹¹ 1985 AC 374, pg.410.

¹² *Ibid*, pg. 407

In line with this decision, the necessary implication of the judgment is that these powers, including those of the Attorney-General, are now subject to judicial review in the same way as the prosecutorial powers of other prosecutors like the Director of Public Prosecutions has long been subject to judicial review.

The Position of the Attorney-General under Nigerian Law

The Attorney-General is the head of the ministry of justice or the minister of justice or the commissioner of justice as the case may be.¹³ Thus, in the case of *Esokoro v. Govt of Cross River State*¹⁴ *per Niki Tobi* rightly commented that:

The Attorney-General is not only the head of the ministry of justice but also the chief legal adviser of the government. He is basically responsible for their actions and inactions.

To qualify as an Attorney-General in Nigeria, Sections 150(2) and 195(2) of the 1999 Constitution provides that:

a person shall not be qualified to hold or perform the functions of the office of the Attorney-General unless he is qualified to practice as a legal practitioner in Nigeria and has been so qualified for not less than ten years

The office and the power of the Attorney-General are well secured and entrenched in the Nigerian law. This position has been recognised under the Nigerian Constitutions since Independence in 1960. The nature and role of the Attorney-General in Nigeria is similar to the role the Attorney-General performs in England and this is traceable to her colonial history. Therefore, in view of the Federal system of Government in Nigeria, there is the position of the Federal Attorney-General and Attorney-General of the State.

¹³ Sections 150(1) and 195(1) makes creation for the office of the Attorney-General of the Federation and States respectively.

¹⁴ (1991) 4 NWLR (Pt. 185) 336.

Attorney-General of the Federation has the power to discontinue any case at any stage of the proceedings without proffering any reason for doing so. The Constitution provides in Section 174(1)(c) thus:

(1) The Attorney-General of the Federation shall have power –

(c) to discontinue at any stage before judgement is delivered any such criminal proceedings instituted or undertaken by him or any other authority or person.¹⁵

Also the Attorney-General of the State has the same corresponding power under Section 211(1)(c) of the Constitution to enter *nolle prosequi* in respect of any criminal proceeding filed either by him or any other person

(1) The Attorney-General of a state shall have power-

(c) to discontinue at any stage before judgement is delivered any such criminal proceedings instituted or undertaken by him or any other authority or person.¹⁶

The Attorney-General of a State or the Attorney-General of the Federation may enter a *nolle prosequi* either by stating in Court or filing appropriate process to inform the court that the state intends that the proceedings abate. Once this is brought to the notice of the presiding judge the accused person shall be discharged immediately.

However, where the Attorney-General delegates his power to enter a *nolle prosequi* to officers of his department or to a private prosecutor, such delegation must be in writing. Thus, a State Counsel cannot enter a *nolle prosequi* or discontinue any criminal proceeding before any court in Nigeria until the instrument authenticating such delegation and effecting such discontinuance is tendered in court.¹⁷

¹⁵ Section 174(c), 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (As Amended)

¹⁶ Section 211 of the Constitution

¹⁷ *State v Chukwurah* (1964) NWLR 64.

It is not within the power of the judge to question the Attorney-General as to why he entered a *nolle prosequi*. The Supreme Court in the case of **Audu v. AG Federation & Anor**,¹⁸ *per Ogunbiyi JSC* held that:

Once the power is invoked, it will not be subject to question either by any person or even the Court.

In Nigeria, this inherent power of the Attorney-General can be used at his discretion and the power can be exercised on behalf of the Attorney-General by any of his authorised officers and it has the same effect as if it is the Attorney-General that entered *nolle prosequi* in person. The Supreme Court in the case of **Ifeacho v. Board of Customs and Excise**,¹⁹ held that:

When a prosecution is conducted in the name of the Attorney-General, he or one of his authorised officers can stop the case by entering a nolle prosequi.

The Exercise of Nolle Prosequi without an Incumbent Attorney-General

The issue of whether the *nolle prosequi* can be exercised by an officer in the Ministry of Justice when there is no sitting or incumbent Attorney-General is a matter of the country that is being discussed. In England, the Solicitor-General is a subordinate of the Attorney-General and he acts on behalf of the Attorney-General if the office becomes vacant or if the Attorney-General is absent or is ill or is authorised by him to do so.²⁰ But in Nigeria, the Attorney-General is the one that is invested with the power which can only be delegated if there is an incumbent Attorney-General. The power can only be delegated to the Solicitor General or any other officer

¹⁸ (2012) LPELR-15527(SC) (Pp. 32-33 paras. F)

¹⁹ (1966) LPELR-25284(SC) (Pp. 5 paras. D)

²⁰ Hood Phillip, *Constitutional and Administrative Law*, (6th Edition) pp.334-336.

in the Attorney-General's ministry if only there is an incumbent Attorney-General. The Supreme Court in the case of *Ezomo v. AG Bendel State*.²¹ The apex Court held that

under the 1979 Constitution, the Attorney-General is the one invested with authority under Section 191 of the Constitution - authority which is personal to him unless, in exercise of the powers granted to him under S.191(2), he delegates any of his powers to officers of his department who would include the Solicitor-General.

Though the power of *Nolle Prosequi* is personal to the Attorney-General and where there is no incumbent/sitting Attorney-General, this power cannot be exercised by Solicitor General unlike other powers of the Attorney-General which can be exercised by law officers in the Attorney-General's office even where there is no sitting Attorney-General and so the Solicitor General cannot exercise this power.²²

However, there is a great departure from the case of *Ezomo v. AG Bendel State* in the case of *Attorney General of Kaduna State v. Mallam Umaru Hassan*²³ where Section 174(1)(c) and Section 211(1)(c) are read along with Section 2 and 4 of Law Officers' Act.²⁴

2. *The offices of Attorney-General, Solicitor-General, and State Counsel are hereby created.*
4. *The Solicitor-General of the Federation in the absence of the Attorney-General of the Federation may perform any of the duties and shall have the same powers as are imposed by law on the Attorney-General of the Federation.*

From the intent and meaning of Sections 2 and 4 of Law Officers' Act, it is manifestly clear that:

²¹ (1986) LPELR-1215(SC) (Pp. 25 paras. B)

²² *AG Kaduna V Hassan* (1985) LPELR-SC.149/1984

²³ (1985) LPELR-617(SC) (Pp. 47-48 paras. A)

²⁴ The Law Officers' Act, Cap L8, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004

1. The Solicitor General of the Federation in the absence of the Attorney-General of the federation may perform any of the duties. This simply means that the Solicitor General has the discretion or choice to perform any of the duties the Attorney-General can perform.
2. The Solicitor General of the Federation in the absence of the Attorney-General shall have the same powers as imposed by law on the Attorney-General of the Federation. This means the Solicitor General of the Federation can exercise the powers conferred on the Attorney-General by virtue of Section 174 of the 1999 Constitution.

In the case of *Saraki v FRN*,²⁵ which provides that in the absence of the Attorney-General, the Solicitor General can competently step into the shoes of the Attorney-General to exercise the powers conferred on him by statute or the Constitution. Therefore, it will not be the correct position of the extant judicial decision to pursue an argument that where there is no person occupying the office of the Attorney-General, activities in the office such as prosecution of offences in the law courts would grind to a halt. It should be noted that the office of the Attorney-General is a creation of the constitution. It is the same constitution that delegated the functions or activities of the office of the Attorney-General to some other persons such as the Solicitor General or other officers in the ministry.

The Supreme Court in the case of *Saraki v FRN*²⁶ in considering the power of the Solicitor General to exercise the functions of the Attorney-General where the office of the latter is vacant held that:

in the absence of the Attorney-General, the Solicitor General or any other officers in the chambers of the Attorney-General can exercise such powers or duties of the Attorney-General relating to institution of criminal proceeding. The solicitor General

²⁵ Supra

²⁶ Supra

while performing the duties and exercising the powers of the Attorney-General in the absence of the latter, can also do so through any law officer in the Federal Ministry of Justice.

That the Law Officers' Act as a complimentary law to the provisions of the constitution gives the Solicitor General the power to competently step into the shoes of the Attorney-General to exercise the powers conferred on him by any statute or the Constitution. The Law Officers Act details the matter of delegation of powers conferred on the Attorney-General by statute on the Solicitor General whenever there is no incumbent Attorney-General in office.

Misuse of Nolle Prosequi

The exercise of the constitutional power of *nolle prosequi* by the Attorney-General, has become a subject of frequent disputes resulting in an avalanche of judicial authorities.²⁷ Notwithstanding the multifarious court decisions, it remains conspicuous that disputes still arise at the exercise of the Attorney-General's power out of miscarriage of justice or the fear of it.

The only check or guiding principles for the exercise of the enormous powers reposed with the Attorney-General includes; public interest, interest of justice and the need to prevent abuse of legal process.²⁸ These must inform the manner in which the Attorney-General exercises his powers. The fact that the Attorney-General is a political appointee and a minister in the executive cabinet. These make it possible for a greedy and power drunk Attorney-General to exercise his constitutional powers to satisfy the wishes of the President or the Governor who appoints him²⁹ and fraudulently couch the reason for the exercise of the power with the

²⁷ Hon Charles Uwensuyi Edosomwan S.A.N., Powers of the Nigerian Attorney-General in perspective, 2006.

²⁸ *Ezea v State* (2014) LPELR-CA/E/303/2010

²⁹ *Onyuike v The People of Lagos State & Ors* (2013) LPELR-CA/L/306/2012

constitutional phrase “in the interest of justice” as provided for in the constitution which states thus:

*In exercising his powers under this section, the Attorney-General of the Federation shall have regard to the public interest, the interest of justice and the need to prevent abuse of legal process.*³⁰

It is a known fact that where the power is abused by the Attorney-General, a miscarriage of justice becomes inevitable. A court system is established for the purpose of justice and nothing else thus making it wrong for the Attorney-General to claim to have exercised the power in the interest of justice.

The issue of the enormous power of the Attorney-General to terminate criminal proceedings instituted against accused persons by officers in his office or by private individuals pursuant to Section 174(1)(c) or Section 211(1)(c) of the 1999 Constitution, as the case may be, would continue to generate controversy so long as there are suspicions by those affected by the exercise of his enormous and unquestionable powers. The Attorney-General being a political appointee of the President or the Governor of a State could be motivated by political or other mundane and not necessarily legal reasons in forming an opinion and coming to a decision, for truncating a criminal trial by the issuance of a *nolle prosequi*. In the case of *State .v. Ilori*, the Supreme Court was called upon to determine the extent of the power of the Attorney General over public prosecution as encapsulated in section 191(1)(c) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1979³¹ . The dictum of Eso, J.S.C. in *The State v. S. O. Ilori and 2 Ors*,³² is very consolatory.

³⁰ Section 174(3) of CFRN 1999

³¹ While section 160 of the 1979 Constitution spelt out the power of the Federal Attorney General over public prosecution, section 191 of the same constitution spelt out the power of the State Attorney General. These are now respectively covered by sections 174 and 211 of the 1999 Constitution. The wording of the sections are however the same.

³² (1983) 1 SCNLR 94 111

The appellant has strenuously harped on the possibility of abuse of his powers by an Attorney-General who is left with his absolute discretion. I have already pointed out earlier, that the sanction lies in the reaction of his appointor and also in public opinion. But more importantly is the fact that a person who has suffered from the unjust exercise of his powers by an unscrupulous Attorney-General is not without remedy; for he can invoke other proceedings against the Attorney-General.

Justice Kayode Eso, who delivered the lead judgment, set out the following statement, which remains the law till date

The pre-eminent and incontestable position of the Attorney-General, under the common law, as the chief law officer of the State, either generally as a legal adviser or specially in all court proceedings to which the State is a party, has long been recognised by the courts. In regard to these powers, and subject only to ultimate control by public opinion and that of Parliament or the Legislature, the Attorney-General has, at common law, been a master unto himself, law unto himself and under no control whatsoever, judicial or otherwise, vis-a-vis his powers of instituting or discontinuing criminal proceedings. These powers of the Attorney-General are not confined to cases where the State is a party. In the exercise of his powers to discontinue a criminal case or to enter a nolle prosequi, he can extend this to cases instituted by any other person or authority. This is a power vested in the Attorney-General by the common law and it is not subject to review by any court of law. It is, no doubt, a great ministerial prerogative coupled with grave responsibilities.

It is quite unfortunate that while resolving the issues raised in *State v Ilori*, the Supreme Court affirmed the common law powers of the Attorney-General and superimposed same on the constitutional provisions in a manner suggestive of a clear intention to disregard other constitutional provisions germane to the just exercise of the power granted the Attorney-

General. With respect to the apex court, the Supreme Court allowed its common law understanding of the Attorney General's power to blur its vision against what the constitution stipulates.

Although the office of Attorney-General is a common feature of the constitutions of all the Commonwealth countries, in jurisdictions like Nigeria, it is the Constitution that confers the Attorney General with similar powers to the common law royal prerogative of his English Attorney-General to exercise ultimate control over prosecutions. With respect, the failure to grapple with the different legal bases of the English and Nigerian Attorney-General's prosecutorial powers is responsible for the Supreme Court's error in *Ilori's case*. The apex court simply abdicated its judicial powers under Section 6(c) and (d) (incidentally Section 6(c) and (d) also under the 1999 Constitution) of the 1979 Constitution which makes it clear that, apart from the two matters specifically excepted by section 6(c) and (d), all other matters, including the exercise of the prosecutorial powers of the Attorney-General, were subject to judicial review under the 1979 Constitution.

Consequently in the case, Chief Justice Fatayi-Williams counseled that:

It is of paramount importance that when an Attorney-General is being appointed, the appointor should, at all times, bear in mind the integrity, ability, experience, and maturity required of the person holding this high and important office. He should be a person who, in the discharge of his duties, will always have regard to the public interest, the interest of justice, and the need to prevent any abuse of legal process.³³

With utmost respect to His Lordships, the Supreme Court in *Ilori's case* fell into error by adopting the presumptive immunity of the English Attorney-General under the common law which has long been subject to judicial review in England.

³³ Supra, pg 112

One wonders how Chief Justice Fatayi-Williams would be feeling if His Lordship were to be alive witnessing the calamitous phenomenon orchestrated by Attorney-General Michael Aondoakaa (SAN). There is considerable evidence to show that the judgment in *Ilori's case* has been a booster and energizer to errant Attorneys-General at both the federal and states levels to undermine the criminal justice system and the rule of law in their respective jurisdictions. It is regrettable, that Mr. Aondoakaa's discontinuation of the criminal proceedings against Orji Uzor Kalu and Jimoh Lawal and his refusal to prosecute the suspects in the Siemens, Willbros and Halliburton corruption scandals, to give a few examples, made such Attorney-General to escape legal challenge because of that decision.

The effect of a *Nolle Prosequi* is that the accused is discharged but he can be prosecuted afterwards with respect to the same offence. Therefore, it is a discharge and not an acquittal.

There is no limit to the number of times that the Attorney-General can enter *nolle* in respect of the same case. His Lordship, Eso JSC said:

Indeed if after a nolle prosequi has been entered, and the court has acted upon it, a fresh or further proceedings on the same indictment are commenced, there is nothing to stop the attorney general from entering yet another nolle prosequi. This he can do as many times as the proceedings rear their heads.

Aniagolu JSC while drawing strength and support from the lead judgment of Eso JSC, said:

The attorney general may, therefore enter a nolle prosequi for as many times as the occasion demands.

His Lordship, Honourable Justice Aniagolu JSC said:

It is appreciated that a nolle prosequi is only a temporary proceedings which has the effect only of a stay and not of a quashing of the indictment, which technically may later be presented without a fresh indictment.³⁴

Furthermore, **Uwais, JSC** (as he then was) in *Attorney-General of Kaduna State v. Mallam Umaru Hassan*³⁵ in retrospect, reiterated the same opinion, to wit:

Following our decision in The State v. S. O. Ilori and Ors, (1983) 1 SCNLR 94 at PP. 111; 116 and 119, it is settled, that where a nolle prosequi is entered in a criminal case, by an Attorney-General, under the provisions of either Section 160 or 191 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999; (sic) (1979) the propriety of exercising the power may be questioned in a civil action which can be brought by a person whose civil rights and obligations have thereby been affected. It follows a fortiori that the exercise of the same power by a legal officer employed in the Ministry of Justice, as in the present case, can be the subject of similar proceedings.

With the pronouncement regarding the powers of the Attorney-General in *State v Ilori*, the question often asked is whether or not the Attorney General is above the courts?

Abuse of Use of Nolle Prosequi in Nigeria

In view of the nature of the power of *nolle prosequi*, which is absolute, unchecked and not subject to judicial review there exist possibilities of abuse of this power by the occupant of the office. Apart from the excesses of the erstwhile Attorney-General Michael Aondoakaa (SAN), another notable example of this abuse was witnessed in the case of *EFCC v Danjuma Goje & 3 Ors.*³⁶ before Hon. Justice B. O. Quadri of Federal High Court, Jos, Plateau where the

³⁴ *Ibid* at pg 82

³⁵ *Supra*

³⁶ <https://corruptioncases.ng/cases/frn-vs-sen-danjuma-goje-former-governo>, Accessed on October 30, 2022

defendants were standing trial on a 21-count charge of corruption in the sum of N25 Billion Naira. While facing trial, he contested the Senate presidency position in 2019 against Ahmed Lawan the presumed favoured candidate. Few days to the election, Senator Goje dropped out of the race and supported Ahmed Lawan, just a few days later the office of the Attorney General took over the prosecution of Senator Goje's case and subsequently discontinued the case. He was subsequently discharged. Instructively, at the time the office of the Attorney General of the Federation entered *nolle prosequi*, there was no incumbent Attorney General as the president was yet to re-constitute his Cabinet. The Court could not question the exercise of powers in the absence of an incumbent Attorney General in view of the principle in **Ilori's case**.

The exercise of this power also violated the principles enunciated by the Supreme Court in **AG Kaduna v Hassan** which decided that there must be an incumbent AG to donate the power to enter *nolle prosequi* before same can be valid. This case gave credence to the call for judicial review of the Ilori's case.

In view of the unchecked nature of the power of *nolle prosequi* which is not subject to judicial review there exist possibilities of abuse of this power by the Attorney-General. A former Attorney General of the Federation³⁷ used the power to terminate several criminal proceedings bothering on corruption. This is a gross abuse of the power of *nolle prosequi* under S. 174(3) of the Constitution.

It is indeed satiric that the principle in *Ilori's case* remains a binding precedent in Nigerian law when the common law practice that the Supreme Court of Nigeria premised its decision on is now otiose in England.

³⁷ The then Attorney General Mr. M.K. Aondoakaa SAN's discontinuation of the criminal proceedings against Dr. Orji Uzor Kalu and Jimoh Lawal and his refusal to prosecute the suspects in the Siemens, Willbros and Halliburton corruption scandals placed him in the negative light before international observers and the Press.

Recommendation

The researchers of this paper humbly recommend that the office of Attorney-General should completely be separated from Ministry of Justice and should not be an appointee of the President or the Governor as the case may be. This is to protect the Attorney General from political dictates. Thus, it is suggested that the Attorney-General, just like the Solicitor-General, should be civil servant as it was in the pre-independence constitutions. If this is ensured, there will be a certain degree of autonomy and freedom from political influence.

The constitutional and discretionary power of the Attorney-General to enter *nolle prosequi* at any stage of criminal proceeding which has been negatively abused by the Attorney-General should be made subject to judicial review by the Nigerian courts so as to check the excesses of the unscrupulous Attorney-General. The courts, particularly, the Supreme Court should be bold to review the use of *nolle prosequi* where it is evident from the subject matter of its use that the power has been abused by the unprincipled Attorney-General.

Conclusion

The roles of the Attorney-General as regards the exercise of *nolle prosequi* in Nigeria and the United Kingdom has been discussed in this paper. The exercise of *nolle prosequi* in Nigeria is traced to English Common Law as one of the colonial relics. The enormous power given to the Attorney General in the Nigerian jurisprudence as well as its abuse are discussed *vis-à-vis* the applicable case laws. After 62 years of independence, the exercise of the power of *nolle prosequi* by the Attorney General as confirmed by the Supreme Court in *Ilori's case* is entirely based on Common Law position and it can be summarized in the dictum of Lord Acton “power corrupt absolute power corrupt absolutely.” It is overdue for Nigeria to take a turn and not only to untie itself from the aprons of the United Kingdom like an overgrown baby firmly attached

to his mother, but also to flow with the tide particularly when the common law principle of *nolle prosequi* being adopted and relied on in Nigeria is no longer good law in England.